

Spinning brush VLV pesticide applicator. A. Brush atomizer. B. Main frame. C. Bevel gear. D. Chemical container. E. Nozzle. F. Deflector.

a wet brush are forcibly deflected and then allowed to bounce back swiftly, a spray of fine droplets is generated.

The pesticide applicator consists of a rotary brush atomizer mounted on the end of a shaft that passes through a pipe frame. The structure is rotated manually with a bevel gear (see figure). An air bleed system is built into the lid of a 1-liter container mounted on the frame. Chemical flows by gravity at a reasonably constant rate and drips onto the brush bristles. A sheet metal deflector generates a spray when the brush is rotated.

Characteristics of spray delivered from different pesticide applicators,^a IRRI.

Equipment	VMD (μm)	NMD (μm)	VMD/ NMD	Swath width (cm)	Droplet density	
					Mean (no./ cm^2)	CV (%)
Brush applicator	187	90	2.07	100	43.1	30.2
Micro ULVA (orange nozzle, 6 V) ^b	105	73	1.43	150	127.5	47.0
CP 15 (HC 60) ^b	90	70	1.28	60	32.9	60.1
CP 16 (Blue)	230	125	1.84	50	81.2	48.3
Tung Ho (H. cone)	200	70	2.85	50	35.5	41.0

^aMention of a commercial product is for specific information only and should not be construed as product endorsement by IRRI.

^bNozzle identification in parentheses.

Droplets from the brush applicator have a volume median diameter (VMD) of 187 μm , smaller than that of knapsack sprayers CP16 and Tung Ho but bigger than that of CP15 and Micro ULVA droplets (see table). The ratio of VMD to number median diameter (NMD) for the brush applicator was 2.07 compared with 2.85 for Tung Ho, indicating greater uniformity in droplet size from the brush.

The brush applicator had a mean droplet density of 43.1 droplets/ cm^2 (CV 30.2%), which is adequate for pesticide application.

The brush applicator applied pre- and post-emergence herbicides as well as other sprayers in replicated field trials. One application of butachlor (1.5 kg ai/ha) reduced weed intensity significantly ($P < 0.05$) from 28.5 g/m^2 in the unsprayed treatment to 5.9 g/m^2 with the brush applicator, 9.7 g/m^2 with a knapsack sprayer, and 4.6 g/m^2 with a spinning disc applicator ($\text{SE} \pm 6.98$).

Mean application rates for the brush applicator were 14.6 liters/ha for butachlor and 12.2 for 2,4-D (CV 0.7-6.1%) with the operator walking at an average speed of 0.5 m/s.

The brush applicator covers a 1-m swath on the operator's right-hand side. The empty applicator weighs about 2.2 kg.

Its operation requires less effort than a knapsack sprayer. It requires 12-15 liters of water and about 6 h to cover 1 ha, whereas a knapsack sprayer requires more than 200 liters of water and 14 h/ha when water is available at the field boundary.

The brush applicator can be fabricated in local workshops and should be marketable for about US\$20.00. A patent application has been filed in the Philippines. Blueprints are available free to interested manufacturers from IRRI's Agricultural Engineering Division. □

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Impact of extension contact on technology adoption

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We investigated the impact of extension contact on technology adoption in a rice-based farming system in Matara District, Sri Lanka. One hundred randomly selected rice farmers were interviewed with the use of a pretested questionnaire. An index was constructed to measure the

degree of adoption of eight innovations: modern varieties, *dapog* nursery, transplanting, chemical fertilizers, chemical weed control, chemical pest and disease control, thresher use, and stubble clearing.

Farmers were grouped into early and late adopters. Frequency of extension visits was nil/few or frequent (at least once in 2 mo). Adopter categories were then cross-tabulated with frequency of extension worker visits (see table)

Twenty-two (85%) of the early adopters received frequent extension

visits compared with 42 (57%) of the late adopters. The χ^2 test indicated a significant relationship (at 0.05 level) between frequency of extension contacts and technology adoption. This implies that with more frequent visits, farmer adoption is earlier. □

Association of extension visit frequency and farmer (n = 100) technology adoption.

Frequency of visits	Early adopters (no.)	Late adopters (no.)
Nil/few	4	32
Frequent	22	42